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9

PREDICTING THE MORTALITY AND NEED OF ICU ADMISSION BY USING VARIOUS SCORING SYSTEM IN PATIENT PRESENT WITH HEMATEMESIS IN EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

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ABSTRACT:

BACKGROUND: An overall annual incidence of acute upper gastrointestinal haemorrhage has been estimated to be 40-150 per 1,00,000 populations ^(1,2), leads to annual hospital admission rate of approximately 100 per 1,00,000 hospital admissions, and has significant associated morbidity and mortality, especially in the elderly. Gastrointestinal bleeding, which is most commonly arises from mucosal erosive disease accounts for up to 20,000 deaths annually.

Various risk scoring systems have been recently developed to predict clinical Outcomes and need of ICU admission in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) or hematemesis. The two commonly used scoring systems include full Rockall score (RS) and the GlasgowBlatchford score (GBS).

MATERIAL AND METHOD: An observational, study was conducted on 50 patients with obvious symptoms of UGIB in the emergency department of SVPIMSR, Ahmedabad. full Rockall score (RS) and the Glasgow-Blatchford score (GBS) were calculated. Data was collected from hospital iHiS system and analysed in epi info (version 7.3.2.1) CDC software. P <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS: A total of 50 patients with UGIB were included in the study of which 72% were male and 28% were female. The mean age of patients was 47.36±16.69 years. It was found that majority of patients (44%) were in the age group of 40-60 years. Mean frequency of hematemesis was significantly higher in non-survival patient in comparison with survival ones (3.1±1.1 versus 1.85±0.62, p=0.0004). In mortality prediction full Rockall score is better than GBS (p value 0.0769 versus 0.9612). Full RS system seems to be better than GBS in predicting mortality and need for ICU admission in patients presented with hematemesis.

KEYWORDS: Hematemesis, Emergency, Mortality

INTRODUCTION:

Acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding remains one of the most common encounters in emergency department that has a high mortality rate. ⁽³⁾ . The extensive clinical spectrum of gastrointestinal bleeding may encompass many different scenarios. The reason for this diversity is bleeding can occur from multiple different lesions and many sites in the gastrointestinal tract.

The prognosis of hematemesis ranges from mild self-limited symptoms to severe hemodynamic instability needs emergent resuscitation and can also even leads to death. ⁽⁴⁾ Moreover, urgent proper triage of the patients in emergency departments and also risk stratification according to risk scoring systems can help to identify patients for urgent diagnostic and therapeutic procedures such as UGI endoscopy ⁽⁵⁾.

Bleeding from upper gastrointestinal tract is approximately five times more common than bleeding from lower gastrointestinal tract. Bleeding may be massive or trivial, obvious or hidden. Gastrointestinal bleeding occurs clinically in one or more of the following four ways.

- 1) Hematemesis (from the upper gastrointestinal tract)
- 2) Haematochezia (from the lower gastrointestinal tract)
- 3) Occult (unknown to the patient)
- 4) Obscure (from an unknown site in the gastrointestinal tract)

Historically, the most common cause of upper gastrointestinal bleeding has been gastro duodenal ulcer disease. Although upper gastrointestinal mucosal lesion account for substantial proportion of cases.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

To predict mortality and need of ICU admission in patient presented with hematemesis by using various scoring systems.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A prospective, observational study conducted during period of June 2019 to March 2020 at S.V.P.I.M.S.R hospital, Ahmedabad-06 Emergency Room of Level-I Trauma centre. 50 patients who presented with obvious symptoms of UGIB including hematemesis (fresh blood or coffee-ground emesis), or melena in the emergency department of SVPIMSR, Ahmedabad enrolled in the study. A Diagnostic endoscopy was performed for patients on admission day or during the hospital stay. Demographic data, vital signs, physical exam findings, laboratory results, history of comorbid illness (e.g., DM, HTN, renal, liver, cardiac, pulmonary disease, and cancer) were recorded on admission. Need for endoscopy, Endoscopic findings, blood transfusion, and intensive care unit (ICU) admission were also recorded. Full RS and GBS systems were calculated for each patient. Pulse rate, systolic blood pressure, blood urea nitrogen, haemoglobin, presence or absence of melena, syncope, hepatic disease, and cardiac failure were recorded as variables of GBS system. Patient's age, systolic blood pressure, pulse rate, presence of comorbid diseases, and endoscopic findings (diagnosis) were recorded as variables of full RS system. All data was collected from ER registry and iHiS record. Data was analysed in epi info (version 7.3.2.1) CDC software.

Inclusion criteria:

All adult patients of both sexes who were giving definite history of vomiting of frank blood or coffee ground coloured vomit and/or passed dark coloured stools were chosen for this study

Willing for part of study Exclusion criteria:

Not willing for part of study

Patients who took DAMA/ LAMA

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

1. SEX DISTRIBUTION (TABLE-I)

A total of 50 patients with UGIB were included in the study of which 72% were male and 28% were female. The mean age of patients was 47.36 ± 16.69 years.

40 patients improved of which 28(70%) were males and 12(30%) females with a mean age of 44.50 ± 16.33 years. 10 patients died of which 8(80%) were males and 2(20%) were females with a mean age of 58.80 ± 13.38 years (p value = 0.013).

2. AGE DISTRIBUTION(FIGURE-I)

It was found that majority of patients (44%) were in the age group of 40-60 years.

The highest age of patient participated in study was 76 years and lowest age of patient was 04 years.

3. QUANTITY OF BLOOD LOSS(FIGURE-II)

It was found that majority of patients 78 % were having minor UGI bleed with < 100ml of blood loss. Only 6% of the patients had major UGI bleed.

Rupture of varices is the most common cause of life threatening hemorrhage. Risk of bleeding is greatest when varices are large and when they are prominent in the gastric fundus. (Lebrec, 1980) (6).

4 FREQUENCIES OF HEMETEMESIS(FIGURE-III)

It was found that percentage of patients with two episodes of hemetemesi was more with 50%.

The maximum frequency of hemetemesi was five.

Single episode of hemetemesi was observed in 12 patients (24%).

Mean frequency of hemetemesi was significantly higher in non-survival patient in comparison with survival ones (3.1 ± 1.1 versus 1.85 ± 0.62 , $p=0.0004$).

5. NEED OF INTUBATION AND MECHANICAL VENTILATION

In this study of 50 patients, 12(24%) patients are found to be hemodynamically unstable and need intubation and mechanical ventilation in emergency department.

6. DISPOSITION (FIGURE: IV)

In the study among 50 patients, 38(76%) patients were admitted in ward and 12(24%) patients were admitted in ICU.

7. ENDOSCOPY

Among the 50 patients in study, 44 patients under goes upper gastrointestinal endoscopy.

8. PREVELENCE OF ENDOSCOPIC LESION (TABLE-II AND FIGURE-V)

In this study among 50 patients, 24 patients (48%) had ESOPHAGIAL VARICES, comprising most common cause of UGI bleed contributing 54% of the total.

It was found that ESOPHAGITIS was the second most common lesion contributing 14% of UGI bleeding.

1 case (2%) of FUNDAL VARICES was noted.

The other acid peptic disorder lesions observed were GASTRIC EROSION 10%, DUODENITIS 4%.

MALLERY WEISS TEARS were observed in 10% of cases.

12% patients found to be hemodynamically unstable and did not underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy.

9. ROCKALL SCORE AND GBS:

The mean full RS was 2.18 ± 1.24 and mean GBS was 9.24 ± 4.15 .

The most and least frequent full RS were 1(38%) and 0(2%) respectively.

In mortality prediction full Rockall score is better than GBS (p value 0.0769 versus 0.9612).

The mean full RS was higher in non-survived patients in comparison with survived ones (2.8 ± 1.13 versus 2.02 ± 1.22 , $p=0.063$).

However, there is no significant difference between mean of GBS in non-survived and survived cases (9.10 ± 4.6 versus 9.27 ± 4.10 , $p=0.9612$).

Mean RS of patients required ICU admission is significantly higher in comparison with patient who need ward admission (2.83 ± 1.11 versus 1.97 ± 1.21 , $p=0.027$).

However, there is no significant difference between mean of GBS in patients required ICU admission and those who were admitted in ward (8.91 ± 4.69 versus 9.34 ± 4.03 , $p=0.98$).

TABLE-I (SEX DISTRIBUTION)

	NUMBER OF CASES	%
MALE	36	72%
FEMALE	14	28%
TOTAL	50	100%

FIGURE-I (AGE DISTRIBUTION)

FIGURE-II QUANTITY OF BLOOD LOSS

FIGURE-III FREQUENCY OF HEMETEMESIS

FIGURE-IV (DISPOSITION OF PATIENTS FROM ED)

TABLE-II PREVELENC OF ENDOSCOPIC LESION

Sr. No.	Nature of Lesion	<10		11-20		21-30		31-40		41-50		51-60		61-70		71-80		TOTAL		TOTAL
		M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	
1	ESOPHAGIAL VARICES	1	1			1	1	1	5		8	2	2	1		1	1	7	7	24(48%)
2	FUNDAL VARICES									1									1	1(2%)
3	ESOPHAGITIS					1	1	1			1		1	1	1			4	3	7(14%)
4	GASTRIC EROSION			1	1	1		1							1			4	1	5(10%)
5	DUODENITIS					1							1					1	1	2(4%)
6	MALLERY WEISS TEAR				1	2		2										5		5(10%)
7	ENDOSCOPY NOT DONE						1		2				2			1		5	1	6(12%)
TOTAL																		50		

FIGURE-V PREVELEENCE OF ENDOSCOPIC LESION

DISCUSSION:

The present study attempted to assess and compare the value of two common applicable risk scoring systems including the full RS and the GBS systems to predict mortality and need for ICU admission in patients with UGIB. Reviewing the literature achieved conflicting results as well as a variety of cut off points for the two-scoring system to predict mortality and need for ICU admission in patient with UGIB. Yang et al in 2016 showed that in predicting mortality, the full RS was superior to the GBS that is same as our study⁽⁷⁾. Lee et al found that the full RS system was more accurate than the GBS system for predicting mortality, same as our study⁽⁸⁾. Mortality rate is 20% in present study as compare to 9.4% in Martinezcara⁽⁹⁾, 18.7% in Daniela Dicu RN⁽¹⁰⁾, 4.8% in Stanley⁽¹¹⁾.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY:

The upper GI endoscopy was not performed by only one gastroenterologist and this may have affected the Full RS estimation.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Full RS system seems to be better than GBS in predicting mortality and need for ICU admission in patients presented with hematemesis in Emergency Department.

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